

Non-functional Requirements Documentation Techniques in Agile Software Development: A Focus Group Study - Online Appendix

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This document provides more details on several aspects of the conducted research study, which had to be omitted in the paper:

- Part 1: The summary results of the literature review.
- Part 2: Descriptions of the investigated NFR documentation techniques.
- Part 3: The list of factors to be considered by the Focus Group participants.
- Part 4: Results from Focus Groups and their analysis.
- Part 5: Examples of validation feedback.

1. Literature review

The Table 1 provides a mapping between the NFR documentation techniques and the sources that list them. The table is followed by the list of all referenced sources.

Table 1. Distribution of sources reporting agile NFR documentation techniques

Technique	Sources	No. of sources
User Stories	[7], [23], [27], [9], [24], [2], [8], [3], [4], [19], [28], [21], [25]	13
Acceptance Criteria	[23], [24], [4], [19], [26], [20], [21], [28], [17]	9
Agile Loose/Use Cases	[10], [14], [11], [12], [13]	5
Prototypes/mockups	[6], [5], [18], [4], [20]	5
Structured Story Cards	[23], [29], [14], [30]	4
Definition of Done	[4], [26], [28]	3
Epics	[4], [21]	2
Traceability Matrices	[1], [25]	2
Framework models	[14], [12]	2
Constraints	[14], [2]	2
Requirement templates	[22], [16]	2
Technical Stories	[28]	1
Features	[15]	1
Tasks	[19]	1
Wiki pages	[4]	1
Whiteboards	[4]	1

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2. NFR Documentation Techniques

2.1. Acceptance Criteria

usually associated with user stories and allow to determine the success of fulfilling a story in the created system. Acceptance Criteria focus on the usability of specific system elements. They define the conditions under which we can consider a created system element as fully usable and fulfilling customer expectations. More generally, they define the desired situations or states of the system. Consider the following user story:

'As the administrator of a web-based booking system, I want to restrict access to the banking system to only users with a valid username and password, so that no unauthorized user can access the data.'

The acceptance criteria for this story might look like the following [26]:

- *'Users with valid usernames and passwords should be allowed to log in.'*
- *'Users with incorrect username and password combinations should be redirected to the login screen.'*
- *'Users with a successful login should be redirected to the home page.'*

If the implemented system element meets all the criteria defined in this way, it can then be stated that it has been implemented correctly and meets the requirement.

However, standard acceptance criteria have some limitations. Such a criterion should refer to only one user story, be based mainly on business rules, and should refer to high-level activities without much detail. Against this, a solution to extend the standard acceptance criteria has been proposed [20]. This solution, called AC+ (acceptance criteria +), allows criteria to be reused between multiple user stories and based on different types of rules or constraints, whether business, technical or validation. In addition, such extended criteria can be defined by each stakeholder and be mainly addressed to the development team, allowing the use of technical language.

2.2. Agile Loose Cases

A new technique proposed in the literature [10], based on standard use cases. They act as instances of specific identified non-functional requirements. They allow a relatively "loose" definition of specific requirements, as quality requirements are usually difficult to define and specify. In general, an Agile Loose Case (ALC) models a high-level non-functional requirement. What's more, it can encapsulate such project management aspects as risk factors, business priorities or estimating volume and effort. Depending on the type, the ALC may store information about aspects of the source code, solution architecture or elements related to the organization's policies. Agile Loose Cases can have interrelationships between them, making it easier to define them and detect possible conflicts.

2.3. Constraints

One possible approach is to treat non-functional requirements as constraints on the functional requirements or the way the target system works. This approach assumes that we can write a quality requirement in the form of constraints or requirements on the rest of the system. Very often, in order for such a requirement specification not to be meaningless, the constraint must be in relation to a specific functional requirement.

Example: Storing password and other user data in encrypted form (a constraint to the functional requirement on user registration in the system).

2.4. Definition of Done

Definition of Done (DoD) is a written standard, a checklist with which we check the completion of each element of a target project. In simpler terms, the project team, together with the client, defines a list of criteria that must be met by an implemented requirement or project element in order for it to be considered “Done” i.e., that the work on it has been fully completed. For this to happen, the element being developed must meet all the criteria on the DoD list. If at least one of them is not met, the implementation of the element cannot be considered completed. Such a precise list of criteria avoids inconsistencies and misunderstandings. It gives a clear picture of the expectations for the system under development and unambiguously defines what work has been done for the implemented part of the project. Unlike Acceptance Criteria, DoD focuses mainly on the feasibility of the project, i.e. specifically on the elements of the system that must be executed, rather than on the usability of the system elements themselves. Moreover, DoD usually covers the entirety of the design work, while Acceptance Criteria usually refers to a small portion of the work to be done.

Examples: An unlogged user does not have access to a resource; The data export option generates a PDF file.

2.5. Epics

An epic represents a larger amount of work that can be broken down into smaller tasks to be completed, based on the needs/requests of customers or end users. In simpler terms, an epic can be considered some large undertaking or large project element to be completed that can be broken down into smaller elements, often specified using other techniques such as user stories.

Example: A user is looking for a job using a job search website. This can be broken down into smaller stories, such as the user can search for jobs by location or salary, the user can view detailed information about the organization that posted the job ad, or the user can apply for a job position.

2.6. Features

A way of specifying non-functional requirements using certain characteristics or capabilities (features). Its main idea is to create certain features of the target product linked to specific categories of non-functional requirements, such as security or performance. Then, based on such created features, we can link other requirements to them in such a way as to determine what must be done/fulfilled in order for a feature related to non-functional aspects of the product to be fulfilled [15].

Examples: Secure authentication, Data encryption (features related to security). Short page load time (feature related to performance).

2.7. Framework models

Non-functional requirements can be specified using a framework designed for this purpose. A framework is a certain template of operation, a way of performing a certain task, using specific tools, techniques or artifacts. With such framework, it is possible to repeatedly perform a certain task on a different set of data. A framework designed for non-functional requirements makes it possible to represent the NFRs in a specific way and to link NFRs to functional requirements in order to present the requirements as a coherent whole.

An example of such a solution was proposed by Farid and Mitropoulos [14]. They present the idea of a framework that uses three types of artifacts to model design requirements. The first is Agile Use Cases, which are a combination of classic use cases and user stories known from agile projects. The second type of artifact is Agile Loose Cases, used to model non-functional

requirements in the form of a loose description of them. The last type of artifact presented by the researchers are Agile Choose Cases, which are potential ways to meet the non-functional requirements written using Agile Loose Cases. Using these artifacts, it is possible to develop the framework, which will be able to describe the non-functional requirements needed to be implemented in the project. Moreover, with such modeling, seeing the connections between non-functional and functional requirements, as well as developing potential ways to provide these requirements, will be much simpler and clearer for project team members.

2.8. Prototypes/mockups

A mock-up is a visual representation of the target product, which, however, is not an interactable program (it is static). A prototype, on the other hand, is a closer approximation of the target product and is an initial, operable version of the product. The main idea behind these techniques is to create a simple initial version of the target software or product. It should not be an entirely implemented target product, but it should be created to the extent that it faithfully represents the target vision of the appearance and operation of the product component.

2.9. Requirement templates

The main idea behind this technique is to develop a catalog of templates suitable for specifying a non-functional requirement. Then, using such templates, the project team can tailor their content to their project. Such templates can be built in a variety of ways, as long as they allow for use when documenting project requirements. One possibility is to use a template written in natural language and containing within it parameters describing specific elements of the system and the requirements for it [16]. Such a sample template might look like the following:

<System element> should have a minimum availability level of <Value>.

2.10. Structured Story Cards

Story Cards are physical small paper cards used to describe high-level requirements from the stakeholder's point of view in a few simple sentences. This primarily serves to understand the stakeholder's point of view and to better visualize the situations in which the target system is to be used. Standard Story Cards are very good for documenting functional requirements, but in the case of non-functional requirements they are no longer sufficient, so it is necessary to structure them by adding, for example, a link to quality attributes or detailed questions specifying the use of a given requirement.

The first example of such a structured story card, is proposed by Um et al. [29]. They extended the standard card with a table of quality attributes and sub-attributes. For each functional requirement described in the card, the key quality attributes most relevant to it (for example, usability, portability or reliability) must be defined. Then, for each quality attribute, the sub-attributes that make up the attribute (for example, usability may consist of such sub-attributes as ease of learning, operability or attractiveness) are defined. By breaking down quality attributes in this way, it is much easier to define the necessary quality requirements for a given functionality, and breaking down attributes into sub-attributes further helps define more specific characteristics of the relevant requirements.

Another example of a card is proposed by Farid and Mitropoulos [14]. It consists of eight categories, named "8 W":

- Who,
- What,
- Why,

ID						
<i>Functional Description :</i>						

<i>Quality Category</i>						
Quality Attributes	Usability	Priority	Portability	Priority	Reliability	Priority
		1		2		3
Sub Quality Attributes	Learnability		Adaptability		Maturity	
	Operability		Installability		Recoverability	
	Attractiveness		Replaceability			

Fig. 1. Structured Story Card example

- Without ignoring,
- While it's nice to have,
- Within (time),
- With a priority of,
- Which may impact (other requirements).

There can be many types of such structured story cards. Each team can create their own card structure depending on the needs of their own project. However, their main idea remains the same - modification of a standard card to define quality attributes essential to a given functionality, and consequently, specification of non-functional requirements associated with a given functionality. An example of a Structured Story Card from [29] is shown in Fig. 1.

2.11. Tasks

Project teams that do not place much emphasis on precise and clear documentation of non-functional requirements can use the task technique to specify them. Tasks are specific work items to be completed, assigned to members of the development team. They are usually simple work items, describing a specific system component to produce, a specific functionality to implement or a specific bug to fix. Such tasks should be simple enough not to take a single developer more than a day's work. This kind of technique can also be applied to non-functional requirements. Instead of creating extensive documentation describing specific non-functional requirements, the team can write such requirements low-level just in the form of tasks. In this situation, requirements are specified by individual tasks, defining how the requirement is to be implemented.

Examples: System login interface, Implementation of data encryption mechanism.

2.12. Technical Stories

Presenting requirements for non-functional aspects of a target product using user stories is not straightforward. Such stories focus on the end user's point of view. For the most part, they do not address the key elements for developers, i.e. how to implement a given quality requirement so that it is met. As a result, an additional technique, so-called technical stories can be applied. Such stories, combined with the context presented in user stories, are able to specify how developers are to address a given non-functional requirement. They present in detail the technical aspects that are needed to be implemented in the target system to meet the specific quality requirement. Example [19]:

Functional Requirements	external quality attribute				
	Usability	Reliability	Performance	Latency	...
FUN1			√	√	
FUN2	√	√	√		
FUN3	√	√	√		
...					
Priority	1	2	3	1	

Internal quality attributes	external quality attributes			
	Usability	Reliability	performance	Accuracy
Maintainability			√	
Flexibility	√			
Portability		√		
...				

Fig. 2. Traceability Matrices

User story: As an online shopper, I want to make sure that my order is complete and correct when I approve it in the online store, so that I can receive the ordered products in the allotted time without mistakes or delays.

Technical story: In order to ensure that only valid orders will be accepted by the system, System A needs to map the order XML file to X, and make the X-form file available to System B, which will run the order validation rules.

2.13. Traceability Matrices

Their main advantage is the possibility of juxtaposing quality attributes with functional requirements or juxtaposing different quality attributes with each other. This makes it possible to analyze contradictions or linkages between different groups of non-functional requirements and other project requirements. An example from the literature (Aljallabi and Mansour [1]): they first divide quality attributes into external and internal. Such a division can vary depending on the assumptions and type of project. The first matrix is constructed by juxtaposing extracted functional requirements and external quality attributes, and indicating which attributes are required by a given functional requirement. After that a second matrix is constructed, this time juxtaposing external quality attributes with internal attributes. This step is used to check potential links or conflicts between the attributes and to assess their importance to the final system. Once this analysis is done and discussed with the customer, the most key quality attributes can serve as the basis for non-functional requirements.

Thus, traceability matrices by themselves are not a way to precisely describe a non-functional requirement. Instead, they allow a very efficient way to analyze requirements, predict contradictions or connections between them and prioritize them for the project, which ultimately facilitates the creation of specifications for such requirements.

An example from [1] is shown in Fig. 2.

2.14. User Stories

One of the most popular techniques used to document requirements in agile projects are User Stories. These are short, usually one-sentence texts that describe how the target system will be used by a particular user. More precisely, these stories illustrate high-level requirements from

the end-user's point of view and justify their business value. In the standard case, user stories specify who the end user is, what they need from the system under development and why they need it. An example of such a story could be the sentence:

'As a user of the payment system, I want to be able to pay my bill online with a credit card, so that I do not have to pay any additional fee.'

Such user stories define precisely what the system under development has to offer and why, which allows the development team to have a good understanding of the requirements placed before them.

User stories are mainly focused on the functionalities to be provided by the system under development. However, this does not mean that they cannot be used to specify non-functional requirements. A properly formulated user story is able to precisely define the requirements for the quality attributes of the product being developed. An example of such a story by Sachdeva and Chung [26]:

'As the administrator of a web-based booking system, I want to restrict access to the banking system to only users with a valid username and password, so that no unauthorized user can access the data.'

This story refers to a security-related requirement. Similarly, user stories can be formulated for other non-functional aspects of the system, such as usability or performance.

2.15. Whiteboards

Project teams use such boards to improve communication about quality requirements among team members. Non-functional requirements are written on the board in the form of their general outline. The whiteboard does not specify the details of such requirements. Instead, teams leave the development of the details to the programmers who are to implement these requirements. A great deal of faith is placed in the programmers and their knowledge and experience that they will be able to clarify and specify the necessary information for each requirement themselves. Programmers may discuss and debate the details of specific requirements during their own meetings (including daily stand-ups), but no additional documentation of such requirements is created. Everything is based on the experience and knowledge of the implementation team. Possible more detailed specifications of non-functional requirements may arise when the requirement in question is not well known to members of the development team.

2.16. Wiki Pages

These are pages that allow its content and structure to be modified collaboratively by multiple users. Project teams use such pages to specify non-functional requirements in the software development process. Their use allows for the concurrent work of multiple team members, who have constant access to the specification of a given quality requirement and at any time can jointly modify its content so that it best meets the expectations of the customer and supports the purpose of the system being developed.

3. The list of factors to be considered by the Focus Group participants

A list of potential factors that could influence the selection of NFR documentation techniques, compiled from the literature. Participants could refer to this list when sharing how they decide which techniques to select, but they could also introduce other factors.

The list included the following items:

- Size of the project team;
- Experience and knowledge of the project team members;

- Preferences of the project team members;
- Working conditions of the project team (remote or on-site, 8-hour workday or non-standard, regular meetings or contact on demand);
- Type of project (business domain);
- Importance of NFRs to the project goals;
- Size of the project;
- Type of NFR;
- Complexity of NFRs;
- Software development method(s) used;
- Additional non-agile methods used (e.g. for project management);
- Number of stakeholders;
- Availability of stakeholders;
- Knowledge of stakeholders;
- Attitude of stakeholders (willing to cooperate or not);

4. Focus Groups - data analysis

4.1. Focus Group A

Table 2. Focus Group A results

ID	Response	Technique
A_1	Some non-functional requirements can be represented as functional ones, e.g., a security requirement can be linked to the need to create an admin panel.	User Stories
A_2	The team prefers to use User Stories because they are associated with agile work.	User Stories
A_3	Specific non-functional requirements for different parts of the system are easy to describe using acceptance criteria.	Acceptance Criteria
A_4	Acceptance criteria define non-functional requirements associated with functional ones described in User Stories.	Acceptance Criteria
A_5	They complement the functional requirements recorded in User Stories.	Acceptance Criteria
A_6	They ensure unambiguous requirement verifiability.	Acceptance Criteria
A_7	Useful when the system should have good User Experience.	Prototypes / Mockups
A_8	Constant non-functional requirements for the entire project.	Definition of Done
A_9	In large projects, they serve as a template for the feasibility of non-functional requirements.	Definition of Done
A_10	A simple and clear way for stakeholders to document non-functional requirements.	Features

ID	Response	Technique
A_11	Requirements such as security, performance, or constraints can be documented in a UML deployment diagram.	Diagrams
A_12	Non-functional requirements lacking user perspective, e.g., agent communication from developers' point of view.	Technical Stories
A_13	They document complex non-functional requirements related to technical aspects, such as integration.	Technical Stories
A_14	Tracking defined and recorded non-functional requirements in large projects.	Traceability Matrices
A_15	Used to ensure requirement verifiability in validated systems.	Traceability Matrices
A_16	Proof of requirement implementation in the system, especially in domain-specific projects, e.g., banking systems.	Traceability Matrices
A_17	Specific fill-in-the-blank sentences, categorized for use or exclusion in a project when team/stakeholder knowledge is low.	Requirement templates
A_18	Used in enterprises operating in regulated markets.	Requirement templates
A_19	High level of formality and documentation requirements, e.g., in public sector projects.	Templates
A_20	Legal regulations related to the business domain impose constraints, e.g., regarding personal data.	Constraints
A_21	A company's detailed security policy regulates project constraints.	Constraints
A_22	Data anonymization requirements are defined by constraints.	Constraints
A_23	Internal team documentation – sharing information about non-functional requirements and their changes.	Whiteboards
A_24	Additional information on non-functional requirements not captured in analytical documentation.	Wiki Pages
A_25	Ability to restrict access to requirement documentation based on permissions.	Wiki Pages
A_26	Use of Confluence, collaboration on non-functional requirements.	Wiki Pages
A_27	Separate document for non-functional requirements, with each chapter for a different requirement category.	Separate SRS Document
A_28	In the RUP methodology, there is a dedicated document for specifying non-functional requirements.	Separate SRS Document
A_29	When it is necessary to meet requirements specified in a standard or legal document (e.g., GDPR), we don't describe them additionally in documentation.	References to Standards / Regulations

4.2. Focus Group B

Table 3. Focus Group B results

ID	Answer	Technique
B_1	The Project Manager suggested using User Stories due to the methodology.	User Stories

B_2	The Scrum methodology enforced the use of User Stories to stay consistent with other teams.	User Stories
B_3	They help refine functional requirements written as User Stories, especially in terms of complex business rules.	Acceptance Criteria
B_4	On the communication line between two teams, they show exactly what needs to be achieved.	Acceptance Criteria
B_5	They easily reveal gaps in non-functional requirements that stakeholders are unaware of.	Prototyping / Mockups
B_6	A prototype was used because there was a risk of missing key non-functional requirements.	Prototyping / Mockups
B_7	Useful for applications with a user interface.	Prototypes/ Mockups
B_8	When stakeholders did not have a clear vision of the requirements, it was easier to visualize the final result.	Prototypes / Mockups
B_9	The project had an evolutionary nature, and the prototype was continuously developed.	Prototypes / Mockups
B_10	Changes in non-functional requirements did not require much documentation—just task creation was enough.	Tasks
B_11	A small non-functional requirement requiring little work.	Tasks
B_12	When there was no time to document requirements as User Stories.	Features
B_13	A different kind of user story: first a functional description, then what non-functional aspects must be met for the feature to be fulfilled.	Technical Stories
B_14	Non-negotiable requirements, high precision—e.g., the need to exchange information with a system updating data every X hours.	Technical Stories
B_15	Other types of user stories: first a business description, then a developer's proposed solution.	Technical Stories
B_16	Purely technical tasks related to non-functional aspects.	Technical Stories
B_17	Showing which functional requirements have satisfied the non-functional ones.	Traceability Matrices
B_18	When the project applies SLA or other regulations (e.g., stability or performance) linked to the business domain.	Constraints
B_19	Legal issues or external tools beyond our control.	Constraints
B_20	Team brainstorming—idea exchange at the early stage of the project.	Whiteboards
B_21	The team had little experience in the project domain (a new project).	Whiteboards
B_22	On-site work—team presence in one place.	Whiteboards
B_23	For a broader description of a complex non-functional requirement.	Wiki Pages
B_24	Additional information about requirements in a self-organizing team.	Wiki Pages
B_25	Sharing information on non-functional requirements using Confluence, GitLab, or MS Teams.	Wiki Pages
B_26	Architecture diagram to show requirements related to data protection or exchange.	UML Diagrams

B_27	They allow the illustration of many different decision paths or business rules related to NFRs e.g. security access privileges based on multiple factors.	Decision Tables
B_28	A checklist to verify whether all elements have been completed.	Definition of Done

4.3. Common themes

Table 4. Selection factors identified from the FG results

ID	Factor / reason for using the technique	IDs of related results
C_1	Specific nature of the non-functional requirement – possibility to express it as a functional requirement	A_1
C_2	Work methodology – Scrum	A_2, B_1, B_2
C_3	Specific nature of the non-functional requirement – various specific requirements for different system components	A_3
C_4	Specific nature of the non-functional requirement – link or refinement of a functional requirement	A_4, A_5, B_3
C_5	Critical need to prove requirement compliance	A_6, A_14, A_15, A_16, B_4, B_17, B_28
C_6	Type of project – importance of User Experience	A_7, B_7
C_7	Specific nature of the non-functional requirement – fixed requirements for the whole system in a large project	A_8, A_9
C_8	Stakeholder knowledge – need for simple requirements	A_10
C_9	Type of non-functional requirements – protection, performance, data exchange	A_11, B_26
C_10	Specific nature of the non-functional requirement – technical requirement without user perspective	A_12, A_13, B_14, B_16
C_11	Low knowledge and experience of the team in the project domain	A_17, B_20, B_21
C_12	Business domain – regulations and supervision over requirements documentation	A_18, A_19
C_13	Business domain – legal regulations, security policies, contracts related to requirements	A_20, A_21, A_22, B_18, B_19
C_14	Way of working – on-site collaboration	A_23, B_22
C_15	Complexity of non-functional requirement – large amount of additional documentation	A_24, B_23, B_24
C_16	Limited access to documentation	A_25
C_17	Way of working – online collaboration	A_26, B_25
C_18	Requirement for a separate document for non-functional requirements	A_27, A_28
C_19	Business domain – standards, legal regulations	A_29
C_20	Stakeholders' knowledge – low awareness of requirements	B_5, B_6, B_8
C_21	Type of project – evolutionary	B_9
C_22	Complexity of non-functional requirement – small requirements or minor changes	B_10, B_11
C_23	Limited time for documenting requirements	B_12
C_24	Way of working – own type of user stories	B_13, B_15

C_25	Specific nature of the non-functional requirement – many different decision paths or business rules	B_27
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4.4. Factors and Techniques Mapping

Table 5. Selection factors and NFR documentation techniques

ID	Factors influencing selection	Documentation techniques
C_1	Specificity of an NFR – it can be described through a functional requirement	User Stories
C_2	Scrum used as development method	User Stories
C_3	Specificity of an NFR – it concerns multiple elements of system architecture	Acceptance Criteria
C_4	Strong association between an NFR and a related functional requirement	Acceptance Criteria
C_5	Necessity to prove that requirements are fulfilled	Acceptance Criteria, Definition of Done, Traceability Matrices
C_6	Project type – key focus on User Experience	Prototypes/mockups
C_7	Specificity of an NFRs – stable requirements concerning the whole system	Definition of Done
C_8	Stakeholder knowledge – low technical knowledge and need for simple requirement representations	Features
C_9	Type of NFRs – security, performance, data exchange	UML Diagrams
C_10	Specificity of an NFRs – purely technical requirement without any user perspective	Technical Stories
C_11	Low team knowledge and experience in the project domain	Requirement templates, Whiteboards
C_12	Business domain – existing regulations regarding requirements documentation	Requirement templates
C_13	Business domain – legal regulations, security policies	Constraints
C_14	Team work conditions – onsite collaboration	Whiteboards
C_15	Complexity of an NFR – large amount of additional information	Wiki pages
C_16	Restricted access to documentation	Wiki pages
C_17	Team work conditions – remote (online) collaboration	Wiki pages
C_18	Separate document required for NFRs	Formal SRS document
C_19	Business domain – standards, legal regulations	References to standards/regulations
C_20	Stakeholder knowledge – difficulty in identifying requirements	Prototypes/mockups
C_21	Software development method used – evolutionary development	Prototypes/mockups
C_22	Complexity of NFRs – simple requirements or minor changes to existing ones	Tasks
C_23	Limited time for documenting requirements	Features

C_24	Team work conditions – decision to customize User Story format	Technical Stories
C_25	Specificity of an NFR – includes many decision paths or business rules	Decision Tables

4.5. Recommendations

Table 6. Recommendations (by NFR documentation techniques)

Technique	Recommendations
User Stories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For NFRs that can be expressed directly by specific FRs. - For Scrum projects, when required by team standards, by decision of the Scrum Master or Project Manager, or when required for collaboration with other teams.
Acceptance Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For describing specific NFRs for various elements of the system under development. - For refining an FR expressed as a User Story by adding related NFRs. - To ensure and prove that the requested NFRs are actually delivered in the project.
Prototypes/ mock-ups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For projects where User Experience is a key issue. - When stakeholders have limited knowledge and cannot clearly define their requirements. - When there is a risk of missing key NFRs due to lack of stakeholder awareness. - For projects based on an evolutionary development approach.
Tasks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For simple, small-scale NFRs that do not require extensive specifications. - For minor changes applied to NFRs that do not require detailed documentation.
Definition of Done	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To ensure and prove that the requested NFRs are actually delivered in the project. - In more complex projects where the list of NFRs is common to all system components.
Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - When stakeholders have very limited IT skills and need the simplest documentation possible. - When there is very little time to spend on the requirements documentation phase.
Technical Stories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For technical requirements without a user perspective. - When there is a need to develop a specific structure for user stories.
Traceability Matrices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To ensure and prove that the requested NFRs are actually delivered in the project.
Requirement templates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - When business domain knowledge within the project team is limited (e.g. first project in a given domain, new team members). - When legal or regulatory requirements impose constraints on the structure and content of requirements documentation in a particular business domain.
Constraints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - When business domain considerations impose requirements on system behavior, e.g., legal regulations, security policies, SLA agreements.

Whiteboards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - When business domain knowledge within the project team is limited (e.g. first project in a given domain, new team members). - For sharing NFRs within a co-located team.
Wiki pages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For storing additional information about NFRs that cannot be included in the main requirements representation. - When it is necessary to restrict access to project documentation (based on roles, security clearances, etc.). - For sharing NFRs within a remote team.
UML Diagrams	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For NFRs related to security, performance, or data exchange.
Decision Tables	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For documenting and analyzing many different decision paths related to NFRs e.g. security access privileges based on multiple factors.
Separate SRS document	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - When NFRs need to be stored in a separate, structured document due to the development methodology used or customer/stakeholder demands.
References to standards/regulations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - When an NFR in the project is defined by an existing official document (standard, legal regulation), and there is no need to describe it in detail (redefine) in the project documentation.

5. Validation example

The expert was provided with the list of recommendations and additional documents explaining necessary related information (e.g., descriptions of the NFR documentation techniques studied). The document with the list of recommendations contained empty placeholders, and the expert was asked to use them to indicate whether or not he agreed with a particular recommendation and to provide additional comments. In case of doubt, he had the opportunity to contact the researcher (the first author) and ask for clarifications. After a few days, the expert completed the task. A short discussion followed as the researcher had doubts about how to interpret some of the comments and asked for additional explanations. An example of the expert's feedback is shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Examples of validation feedback

Technique	Recommendations	Agreed?
Requirement templates	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - When business domain knowledge within the project team is limited (e.g. first project in a given domain, new team members). - When legal or regulatory requirements impose constraints on the structure and content of requirements documentation in a particular business domain. 	Yes
<p>Comment: Does not represent the knowledge about requirement by itself, it is rather a pattern for e.g. User Story or task. From my experience they are usually presented at the beginning of the project to achieve more consistency in documenting requirements. Templates establish some convention for documenting.</p>		
Constraints	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - When business domain considerations impose requirements on system behavior, e.g., legal regulations, security policies, SLA agreements. 	Yes
<p>Comment: Usually, I stumble across the approach that the system constraints that need to be taken into account are gathered in one place. If necessary, any member of the project can access them.</p>		